

PROMOTION OF HUMAN DIGNITY - THE MAIN CRITERIA OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE STATE AND SOCIETY

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Abstract: this article evaluates the concept of “human value” based on a philosophical and social approach. The author tries to shed light on human value not only from a legal or political point of view, but also from a moral, spiritual and ontological point of view. It also extensively analyzes the fact that the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy places human values at the center, and that a democratic society is being built on the basis of the constitutional rights, freedoms and principles of social equality of citizens. It reveals how human values are manifested through the development of the mahalla institution, social protection and citizenship reforms. The article analyzes the views of philosophers such as Socrates, Kant, and Al-Farabi on the essence of man, in harmony with modern reforms.

Keywords: human value, philosophy, value, spirituality, constitution, citizenship, democratic society.

Human dignity is not simply a position or external respect in society, but a fundamental concept related to the existence, freedom and spiritual elevation of a person. In philosophy, the place of a person in this world, the meaning of life, freedom, moral responsibility and dignity have long been an important object of research. Socrates' call to "Understand yourself!", Immanuel Kant's idea of "always seeing a person as a goal", the concepts of striving for spiritual perfection put forward by Ibn Sina and Al-Farabi have not lost their relevance today. It is not for nothing that in the era of new Uzbekistan the idea of "For the sake of human dignity" has become the main priority of state policy. Because at the center of development is a person, who is worthy of all-round attention, respect and protection. Human value is being rediscovered today not only as a legal and social criterion, but also as a moral, philosophical and universal value. In this regard, the understanding of a person as a value, the analysis of his place in society, his personal and social essence, has become one of the main issues of modern philosophy.

The article also reveals the interrelationship between human interests and the system of values. In this system, a person's value is formed through his rights and freedoms, moral choices, participation in society, his attitude to work, the environment, and other people. In order for each person to feel valuable in society, the state must create the necessary conditions for legislative foundations, information openness, social equality, and spiritual and cultural development.

The main purpose of the article is to use philosophical approaches in understanding human values, combine them with social practice, and propose theoretical and practical solutions.

The concept of "human dignity" includes the comprehensive provision of human rights and freedoms and legitimate interests. As stated in Article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, "All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights" (Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Article 1 [2]).

According to Article 13 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Democracy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on universal human principles, according to which a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inalienable rights are considered the highest value" [1].

Article 13 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that everyone has the right to freedom of movement and residence within the borders of each state, to leave any country, including his own, and to return to his own country.

In short, every person living in our country is witnessing in practice that the firm will and principle of the Head of State: "No one should ever forget: no matter how difficult it is, no matter how much money and opportunity are required, no citizen of Uzbekistan will be left to his own devices" is being confirmed in our lives (Sh. Mirziyoyev, [5]).

According to the author, human dignity is a concept that means the glorification of the human race as the greatest miracle of God, gaining all-round dignity. In understanding the criteria of values for a person, the family environment, parents, relatives, and teachers play an important role. It is on the basis of these factors that a person matures. Throughout his life, a person strives to improve his personal values, to perfect his own value, to understand his place in society. In order to understand the value of himself and others, a person's spiritual world must serve goodness, have high social qualities, and he himself must be educated to the point of correctly understanding the essence and

purpose of life. In this sense, Socrates' call to "Know thyself!" is important. There are objective, subjective, social and personal aspects of understanding one's own value, which constantly live in interrelation, reflecting various aspects of human nature [6].

The value of each person is reflected in the mirror of the time in which he lives, the processes in it, and the socio-historical conditions. The requirements of the environment and era shape and elevate the value of a person. He himself, as a subject of social relations, increasingly realizes how much his value is connected with his personal requirements, needs and goals.

The problem of man and his value is one of the ancient topics of philosophy. The issues of the birth of the human race, its difference from other creatures, its place in nature and society, human qualities, and personal characteristics have been the focus of attention of philosophers of all times. As is known, the study of the physical structure and natural-biological characteristics of man still continues in the world of science. In the social sciences, issues related to the development of the individual, his social and spiritual image are being studied. Thus, for mankind, problems related to other people similar to him, their characteristics, place in society, value, past and future have long been the main object of research and observation. The interpretation of a person as a value is different from the issues of his value and the system of values at the personal level. In this regard, one can think in three directions. First, each person can be considered as a value. In this, the person himself, his existence in the natural-historical process, the only social entity among living creatures is taken into account. The analysis in this direction is specifically aimed at a person, making him the object of a special research topic. Second, it is also possible to study issues such as the value of a person, that is, his place in social processes, his significance for the environment and other people, and his position in society. Such an analysis is based on the study of the socio-historical significance of a person. Third, it is also possible to analyze the system of values associated with the spiritual world, image, world of interests, demands and needs, and activities of a person. In this case, the main attention is paid to the forms and characteristics of the manifestation of values at the personal (separate, individual) level. In the present era, the value of every person is clearly visible, first of all, in his attitude towards nature, the processes taking place in the external world, his role and activity in these processes, towards people belonging to different races, nationalities, social strata, striving for diverse goals and values, towards himself, towards his position in the family, life, community

and society. Also, his participation in the processes of labor, production and the economy, his contribution to the satisfaction of social needs in society and the creation of material wealth, determines the value of a person.

In addition, the activities related to political changes, participation in the democratization of society, what goals they pursue in this process, and what position they occupy and how they behave in today's rapidly changing value system are also of particular importance in this regard. In addition, human dignity is manifested through their knowledge, spiritual level and social activity. These qualities determine a person's place in society. In this regard, their correct understanding of the essence of various destructive ideas, destructive ideologies and other heresies, and their attitude towards them are also important. Taking into account all these aspects, it is possible to assess human dignity and determine types of individuals on this basis.

Human interests are one of the forms of social interests, a concept that means directing the main goal of changes and development in society to a person, ensuring the priority of human rights. Human interests are based on the principles of the priority of human needs, interests, rights and freedoms, ensuring its special place and importance in society as the greatest wealth, and rationally establishing mutual relations between society, the state and man. As is known, 1997 was declared the "Year of Human Interests" in our country. In the Year of Human Interests, even greater importance was given to the human factor. In naming the following years and determining the priority direction for our country, human interests are taken into account, first of all, as a priority issue. "For the sake of human dignity" is a priority principle in the Constitution, no one can be imposed on an obligation not established by law without his consent. The fact that a person has been convicted and the legal consequences arising from it cannot be a basis for restricting the rights of his relatives. Everyone has the right to a comfortable environment and reliable information about his condition. Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data, the right to demand the correction of inaccurate data, the destruction of data about him that was collected unlawfully or no longer has a legal basis. The state creates conditions for the organization of the activities of national human rights institutions. The state creates conditions for ensuring citizens' access to the global information network the Internet. The rights of victims of violations are protected by law. Ensuring human rights and freedoms is the supreme goal of the state. Human rights and freedoms are recognized and guaranteed in accordance with international law and the Constitution.

Human rights and freedoms determine the essence and content of laws, the activities of state bodies, citizens' self-government bodies and their officials. Human rights and freedoms belong to everyone from birth. A citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan may not be forcibly expelled from Uzbekistan or extradited to another state. The death penalty is prohibited in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Everyone has the right to protect his rights and freedoms by all means not prohibited by law. Human honor and dignity are inviolable. Nothing may be a basis for degrading the honor and dignity of a person. Everyone has the right to free development of his personality[4].

What is human dignity? Why has this word been used so often in recent years? It is increasingly taking a firm place in our lives.

Human dignity occupies a special place in folk folklore. This can be observed through expressions such as 'I did not reach my dignity', 'Is this my dignity?' So human dignity must be above all material wealth. There is no criterion for human dignity. A person deserves unlimited appreciation. At this point, a question arises. Valuing a person is an important task of society and the state. Who governs the state and society? Of course, it is carried out under the leadership of the President.

The Head of State firmly demands that in our country, the honor and dignity of a person are inviolable, that nothing can be a basis for their humiliation, and that the principle of "For the sake of human dignity" must be the main criterion in the Constitution, our laws, and the activities of state agencies. In this regard, as a result of the reforms being carried out in our country, including the constitutional processes, the number of norms serving human dignity and interests in our Constitution has increased by 3 times compared to the current one [3].

Ensuring the rights and freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens is one of the priority areas of democratic renewal. In this process, human rights can be ensured by strengthening parliamentary control over the activities of state and economic management bodies, judicial and legal bodies, as well as officials - state officials.

In short, human dignity is determined not by a person's biological existence, but by his free thinking, spiritual growth, ability to find his place in society, and respect for others. In order for a person to be valued and recognized, society, the state, and each individual must be mutually responsible. This value is realized not only through legal guarantees, but also through each person's self-awareness, empathy for others, and adherence to moral principles.

In seeking an answer to one of the eternal questions of philosophy - "Who is a person?", we try to deeply understand human value. A person is not only a participant in social relations, but also a being with a spiritual world, who thinks, feels, and has the ability to make choices. Therefore, glorifying human value is not only a legal obligation, but also a moral and spiritual duty.

The fundamental reforms and constitutional reforms being implemented in the conditions of the new Uzbekistan are helping to reflect human values in real life. In these processes, the highest human virtue is for each person to realize their own value and dedicate it to the development of society.

In today's conditions of globalization, digital transformation and cultural diversity, preserving and further enhancing human values has become an urgent task. In this regard, philosophy is an important tool for seeing a person as a value, awakening his consciousness, forming moral criteria, and strengthening social solidarity. By understanding human values, it is possible to establish an atmosphere of high human relations, mutual respect, tolerance, justice and solidarity in society.

Human values are not only a set of principles set forth in legal documents, but are also reflected in the moral relations, spiritual growth, self-knowledge and high respect for others that are manifested in the daily life of each person. A person who understands his own value becomes active in society, approaches social life responsibly, consciously builds his life and future. Therefore, strengthening human values is a strategic basis for the development of the state and society.

Human value is the most important advantage that brings humanity, kindness, justice and social solidarity to our society.

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